

Paper ID #

Data-driven mobility services based on connected vehicles and infrastructure

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Abstract

Urban areas are equipped with many real-time traffic monitoring sensors including traffic camera, detection loops, vehicles' GNSS sensors which can be used to offer new mobility services. Indeed, cities are aiming to improve mobility to their citizens, i.e make it safer and more efficient. Therefore, we are proposing a new mobile application which can dynamically adjust travel route of users, including ride sharing, and provide parking information. Based on such applications, citizens can have a better experience in the usage of transport systems and cities can optimize their offer. In this paper, we describe the proposed solution which is built on top of vehicles & roadside sensors and 5G network component. Cloud services to predict traffic jam and a mobile application have been developed and initial deployment and testing have been done to demonstrate the approach.

Keywords: 5G, MEC, Cloud, Connected and Automated Mobility, Mobile Application

Introduction

Due to the constant rush, we live in, time matters more than anything in today's society. Everyone is looking for applications and devices that allow them to save time and energy. Fortunately, today's technology has made this possible. The Uber concept is one interesting example that demonstrates how customers are now looking for convenience as a priority feature in their software products. The number of Uber's active users worldwide has escalated from 49 million in the first quarter of 2017 to 111 million in the last quarter of 2019 [1]. The considerable growth of smart speakers / virtual assistants that saves the owner a few minutes of typing what music he/she would like to hear or what's tomorrow's weather like is another reflection of today's consumers' priorities. Whether it is Siri from Apple or Alexa from Amazon, smart speakers see their sales reaching 147 million units globally in 2019, resulting in 70% growth over 2018 [2].

On one hand, Connected and Automated Mobility (CAM) has allowed today's vehicles not only to use data but also to generate useful data through their on-board sensors (e.g., LIDAR). CAM has also enabled the extension of the road actors to include Connected Road-Side Units (RSU) (also called Road-Side Infrastructure (RSI)), Multi-Access Edge Computing (MEC) servers, and even pedestrians' smart devices considered as edge nodes, resulting in an even more significant amount of data generated on the transport sector. As these data need to be transmitted and subsequently processed to create actual value, 5G live messaging ensures that these data can be transmitted from one vehicle to another (V2V) and/or to other RSUs (V2I) and eventually to third parties (V2X) that can use them also to create different innovative services.

On the other hand, 5G enables up to 100 times the number of connected devices per unit area than 4G-LTE, reaching a high density of devices (about 300.000 devices in a single cell) [3] that can be connected to each other. This key feature of 5G is named massive Machine Type Communications (mMTC), which, as its name suggests, provides connections to large numbers of devices that transmit small amounts of traffic among each other. This characteristic enables a highly cooperative smart city, where vehicles are capable of e.g., enhancing each other's perception in case of obstacles, sharing itineraries to avoid traffic congestions. Basically, it leverages a full location awareness to every road actor and promotes highly harmonized roads with lesser accidents and traffic.

As people can benefit from a large offer of transportation means and are expecting to take a solution that suits well their needs in terms of travel time, comfort, cost, etc., digital platforms are expected to offer access to many services to facilitate users' mobility, one example can also be referred with the term Mobility as a Service (MaaS). To be efficient and reliable, these new technologies require a large amount of data, for instance, to predict road traffic, detect incidents and offer alternatives in almost real time, to users. Motivated by the large capacity of 5G to offer the opportunity to connect thousands of devices per unit area, we are developing a new mobile application which can offer parking and navigation services within metropolitan areas based on data can be aggregated from multiple data sources such as vehicles, roadside infrastructure or traffic management centres. This application is thus enabling the monetization of data in the context of a dynamic route planning and networked parking use case of the 5GMETA project as illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Illustration of dynamic route planning and networked parking use case

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section 2, “Proposed solution”, describes the innovative

application, Section 3, “Implementation and Results”, proposes an implementation approach and initial results related to this mobile application. Finally, Section 4 concludes this work.

Proposed solution

Connected mobility services are relying on digital content exchanged through different channels, aiming to enhance the experience of users along their travels. In a local territory, e.g. a city, many challenges exist related to road users’ mobility such as the management of traffic and parking, optimization of journey routes, announcement of points of interest and of unpredicted events. Hence, considering that a data platform can provide many data from connected vehicles, roadside infrastructure sensors, public authorities or road operator servers, to a mobile application targeting those challenges. With such mobile application, a user can be able to plan its trip within the city and arrive on time to its target destination. Two principal components have been developed as part of such innovative services and have been deployed in cloud servers:

- “Lazarus” is the main application for hosting the different mobility services and is composed of two parts: cloud hosted components, which are in charge of heavy processing upon users’ requests; and a mobile application, which is available on end user devices to access the services.
- “Traffic Jam Detection & Prediction” is the core application that can consume data from sensors and devices (roadside and vehicle sensors) to train accurate models of the road traffic and to monitor traffic conditions in real-time.

These two components are interacting so that an itinerary planned at the request of a user is well adapted depending on different conditions:

- Expected departure/arrival location and time
- Parking spots availability
- Occurrence of an unlikely event, e.g. route blockage
- Existence of public events
- Requirement to plan intermediate stops for car pooling

Figure 2 shows a high-level architecture of the proposed solution, which are required to implement the related services. As illustrated, such services are based on uplink data flows exchanged through a dedicated data platform deployed in MEC server. From the data processed at the cloud server layer, “Lazarus” component can provide relevant information to the end users.

Figure 2: High-level architecture of the proposed solution

In addition, Table 1 describes the different modules of the proposed solution.

Table 1: Description of Solution Modules

Layer hosting the module	Module name	Module description
End user client	Lazarus Client	A mobile application which allows user to connect to the Lazarus server in order to have an itinerary and an available parking spot at the arrival.
Cloud Servers	Lazarus server	The Lazarus server is the API between the Lazarus app and the other modules. It is also the database of the users (user information, Map tiles, routing server, etc.).
	Traffic Jam Detection and Prediction	The Traffic Jam Prediction is used to estimate the future congestion of roads for a given itinerary while detection allows to monitor real-time traffic data.
Vehicle & Roadside Infrastructure	Onboard perception	Onboard perception provides lists of objects (vehicles, pedestrians) that can be detected by a vehicle.
	Vehicle telemetry	Vehicle telemetry provides the location of a vehicle usually using a GNSS device.
	Roadside perception	Roadside perception comprises lists of objects detected from a roadside infrastructure. It also includes live stream of roadside cameras feeds.
	Roadside Unit	Roadside unit are able to extend radio coverage to vehicles not equipped with 5G Cellular Network and act as a gateway to forward messages (e.g. CAM/DENM/CPM).
	Traffic &	A traffic monitoring server uses sensors deployed in the

Figure 4: Vehicles equipped with on-board unit and sensors

Figure 5: roadside sensors & roadside units

The Lazarus server is a RESTful API implemented in Python using the framework Flask. The Framework is used to create the API and to add multiple functions that will be used to access to function on the server through the API.

In the screenshots depicted in Figure 6, Lazarus application screens are shown. The first one is the login interface which the user type his/her email and password to sign in. Then, if login successes, the next interface comes in. It is a destination bar where the user types his/her destination. Suggestions are displayed to help the user to type the destination faster. Then when the itinerary is launch, the user can see a screenshot of real-time navigation with the Lazarus App.

Figure 6: Screenshots of Lazarus Application

To feed the Lazarus application with data, a set of roadside sensors which can detect vehicles equipped with Bluetooth devices and periodically send the captured data to a dedicated server have been

deployed. A log file is generated every 5 minutes with the information of captured Bluetooth beacons (timestamp, channel number, part of MAC address, clock frequency of the device, clock offset, signal to noise ratio...). Then, the number of vehicles is obtained by filtering the data for other devices to remove pedestrians and stationary devices. Finally, capture data are processed to assess two metrics:

- Throughput: It is defined as the number of vehicles (number of unique MAC addresses after performing the filter mentioned above) detected every 5 minutes.
- Occupation rate: Sum of the travel time for each vehicle for a given time window)/(Time window * Max. number of vehicles)

Figure 7 illustrated the throughput of traffic captured at different hour of the day with the deployed sensors.

Figure 7: Illustration of traffic detection based on Bluetooth detection

Then, the goal is to develop a powerful model that can predict traffic jam to help Lazarus plan an optimized itinerary. To achieve this, the innovative services devised into three main steps:

- 1) Detect jam with a network of points: An API which flags an alert when several requests are performed on the same bunch of points was developed.
- 2) Train model for the prediction occupation rate.
- 3) Predict the traffic upon request by the Lazarus application.

To train the model, the open dataset provided by Paris [4] which contains traffic measurements in Paris from January to March 2022, was used. We have initially focussed our training and tests on the “rue de 4 Septembre” street to develop a model based on random forest as illustrated in Figure 8.

Figure 8: Model learning to traffic jam prediction

Finally, Figure 9 illustrates the prediction of occupation rate for one week based on the trained model.

Figure 9: Prediction of occupation rate during one week

Conclusion

In conclusion, 5G technology has the potential to significantly improve the ability to gather datasets for the development of new mobility service in metropolitan areas. By collecting data from multiple IoT devices, we have developed a mobile application which can dynamically adjust route to changes in the environment and propose parking solution to citizens. The proposed solution has been initially tested in a limited environment and with public dataset. Future work can include the addition of additional data sources and extension to large perimeter, e.g. at the scale of city.

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